

Reformatsky Reaction in Imines: Synthesis of β -Lactams

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Reformatsky reaction provides a useful route to β -hydroxy esters. The chemistry of imines have been reviewed in comparison to $>C=O$ compounds¹. Gilman² and Speeter² described for the first time the formation of a β -lactam from benzylidene aniline and ethyl α -bromo acetate under the conditions of this reaction. The present report elaborates this reaction by taking different substituted aromatic imines and aims at the evaluation of the role of electronic factors on the course of the reaction.

The imines were prepared by condensing aldehydes and amines in methanol as usual. The imines dissolved in dry toluene and clean zinc are placed in a three necked flask and ethyl α -bromo acetate was added dropwise. After the completion of the reaction and usual work up, the residue on crystallisation from methanol gave the white crystalline products. The characteristics and the elemental analysis of these compounds are recorded in Table-I. The i.r. spectrum of these compounds showed bands well above 1740 cm^{-1} indicating the formation of β -lactam.

It has been found that strongly electron withdrawing in the imine part inhibit the reaction. Benzylidene *p*-nitro aniline gave no characterisable β -lactam, instead gave resinous material. Same was the fate of this reaction when *p*-nitro benzylidene aryl amines were used. This reaction was also attempted on conjugated imines derived from cinnamic aldehyde and differently substituted aromatic amines. The reaction in these conjugated aromatic imines gave no crystalline product, instead gave resinous material. This reaction seems to be a good preparative route to the formation of β -lactams which in turn have good physiological value.

EXPERIMENTAL

The aromatic non-conjugated and conjugated imines were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of appropriate aldehydes and amines in methanol at room temperature or under reflux. The imines were obtained by usual workup and were crystallised from petroleum ether or methanol.

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1. R. W. Layer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 463.

2. H. Gilman and M. Speeter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 2255.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	X	Y	m.p. of bases °C	m.p. of Lactams °C	Solvent of Crystallisation	Yield %	I.R. Frequency cm ⁻¹	Analysis					
								Calc. %	Found %		Found %		
							C	H	N	C	H	N	
1.	H	H	52	155-56	Methanol	58	1740	80.71	5.82	6.28	80.59	5.74	6.10
2.	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	62-62.5	100-101	Benzene	54	1756	69.90	4.66	5.43	69.75	4.48	5.30
3.	H	<i>p</i> -Br	65-67.5	130-131	Benzene	59	1746	59.60	3.97	4.64	59.42	3.86	4.50
4.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	—	152-153	Benzene	60	1750	76.40	6.37	5.24	76.32	6.21	5.00
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	63-64	159-160	Methanol	64	1760	69.90	4.66	5.43	69.72	4.42	5.00
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	—	147	Methanol	57	1755	53.49	3.27	4.16	53.34	3.10	4.10
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	109-110	157-158	Methanol	63	1748	61.85	3.78	4.78	61.72	3.64	4.30
8.	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	66-67	125-126	Benzene	68	1753	53.46	3.27	4.16	53.22	3.15	4.00
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	68	132-133	Methanol	70	1763	61.85	3.78	4.78	61.76	3.59	4.50

A solution of 18.1 gm (0.1 mole) of benzylidene aniline in dry toluene (100 cc.) was heated to boiling with 6.75 gm (0.1 gm atom) of pure zinc foil and a crystal of iodine. Three cc. of ethyl α -bromo acetate was added and on stirring an exothermic reaction set in. Ten more cc. (a total of 0.1 mole) of α -bromoester was now added at such a rate as to maintain gentle refluxing. When the addition was complete, the mixture was boiled gently for one and half hour. Hydrolysis was effected with 100 cc. of concentrated ammonium hydroxide. After this the toluene layer was separated and washed with water, dilute HCl, sodium bisulphite solution and again with water. After the distillation of the solvent and repeated crystallisation from methanol gave, as crystalline white compound m.p. 153-54° (56% yield).

The same procedure was adopted for the preparation of other β -lactams.

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